

PROBLEMS OF USING NEW INTERACTIVE METHODS AND PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *In this article, problems of using of new interactive methods and pedagogical technology are raised. According to the author, interactive methods and new pedagogical technology are considered modern advanced methods. As the author points out that, the widespread use of modern computer technologies in the educational process, along with the use of multimedia systems and distance learning tools in teaching foreign languages, has become extremely important. The author indicates the key problems in this sphere.*

Key words: *communication, development, education, framework, information, interactive, language, methods, modern, multimedia, pedagogical, technology.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada yangi interfaol usullar va pedagogik texnologiyadan foydalanish muammolari ko'tariladi. Muallifning fikricha, interfaol metodlar va yangi pedagogik texnologiya zamonaviy ilg'or uslublar hisoblanadi. Muallif ta'kidlaganidek, xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda multimedia tizimlari va masofaviy o'qitish vositalaridan foydalanish bilan birga ta'lim jarayonida zamonaviy kompyuter texnologiyalaridan keng foydalanish nihoyatda muhim ahamiyat kasb etdi. Muallif ushbu sohadagi asosiy muammolarni ko'rsatadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *aloqa, rivojlanish, ta'lim, ramka, axborot, interaktiv, til, usullar, zamonaviy, multimedia, pedagogik, texnologiya.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье поднимаются проблемы использования новых интерактивных методов и педагогических технологий. По мнению автора, интерактивные методы и новые педагогические технологии считаются современными передовыми методами. Как отмечает автор, широкое использование современных компьютерных технологий в образовательном процессе, наряду с использованием мультимедийных систем и средств дистанционного обучения в преподавании иностранных языков, стало чрезвычайно важным. Автор указывает ключевые проблемы в этой сфере.*

Ключевые слова: *коммуникация, развитие, образование, структура, информация, интерактивный, язык, методы, современный, мультимедиа, педагогический, технология.*

Students' perception or memorization of object information, data, material can be of varying degrees, depending on the method, methods, means, and conditions used. According to scientists, usually only 10% of the text read is remembered. When listening, 20% is remembered. Only 30% of what we watch is remembered. If we both watch and listen, then 50% of the lesson passed, and we ourselves tell it, then we remember 70%. If we tell the subject, then we remember 90% of the subject matter that has been studied. According to well-known linguists, the use of modern information technologies in the higher education system creates the following advantages. 1. It provides students with a wide range of opportunities, that is, studying the subject-object using multimedia systems (for example, a standard CD-compact disk with a capacity of 650 megabytes is capable of storing 300-325 thousand book-pages, which creates an incomparable opportunity to save both time and) labor. 2. It creates the opportunity to repeatedly demonstrate and simulate the mastered educational materials. 3.

With the help of a special computer program, it is possible to speed up or slow down the process of enlarging the size and volume of the subject, to study it more thoroughly. 4. With the help of virtual images, it is possible to depict conditions that cannot be created in a simple natural situation using a computer and display the results of experiments of various sizes on the screen. In the same way, the student can explain the subject at his own will, speed up or slow down the process of explanation, or stop at certain situations if necessary.

At the present stage of development of society, knowledge of English is becoming very important. There is no need to convince anyone of the necessity to learn a foreign language, life itself testifies to this. TV programs are broadcast in English, scientific literature is published, modern songs are played and foreign films are shown, in addition, instructions for various household appliances are written in English, etc. In most cases, if there is a translation, it is not always correct and therefore learning English is very relevant. But to make the process of mastering the language more effective, it is necessary to use interactive teaching methods.

Recently, the widespread use of modern computer technologies in the educational process, along with the use of multimedia systems and distance learning tools in teaching foreign languages, has become extremely important. Distance learning technology includes interactive audio, video, electronic printed materials, audio cassettes, video cassettes, television and radio broadcasting means of delivering educational material to listeners. Each method of distance learning has its own educational technologies and distance learning tools. However, both methods are closely interconnected and complement each other. Multimedia, in turn, involves the development and use of modern English electronic textbooks and various multimedia computer materials. Interactive methods of education have been developed mainly in the last two decades. Currently, interactive methods are considered modern advanced methods and are widely used. Today, their number has exceeded 60. The essence, goals, and objectives of these methods were described by the linguist O. Khoshimov who was engaged. Interactive methods involve the activation, development and use of the huge educational potential of students. Interactive methods of education are currently being used in many methodological technologies in developed countries. Interactive education is the study of dialogue, monologue speech, communication, in which there is a dialogue between the teacher and the student, students, and the computer. Interactive education is a special form of knowledge, communication, and organization of activity. This education implies a completely clear and predictable (predictable) goal. Creating favorable conditions for education is one of these goals. In this case, students feel that they are successfully learning, their intellectual depth. Today's educational process should be clearly aimed at developing students' critical and creative thinking. The main task of students is to learn productively, think critically and creatively, and master. Today, the communicative method is the most popular in learning foreign languages. The main goal of this method is to teach a person to interact with other people in the language being studied, which implies all forms of communication: speech, writing, the ability to listen and understand what the interlocutor says. Discussion is one of the types of interactive educational technologies. Computer simulations, business game, Case technology, Lecture with errors, Brainstorming, Video conference and Webinar are also very popular methods in education process.

Group discussions are usually conducted on a specific topic and are aimed at finding the right solution and achieving better mutual understanding. Group discussions contribute to better assimilation of the material being studied. At the first stage of group discussion, students of non-linguistic universities are given an assignment for a certain time, during which they must prepare a reasoned, detailed answer. The teacher can establish specific rules for conducting group discussions.

Training is a form of interactive learning, the purpose of which is to develop interpersonal communication skills and professional behavior in communication. The advantage of training is that all

participants are actively involved in the learning process. Discussion is a student-centered learning activity. It is characterized by active interaction between students and intensive, student-centered learning by the teacher. The advantage of discussion is that it shows how well the group understands the problem. The "brainstorming" method is a fairly popular method of solving problems by stimulating creativity. According to this method, the teacher asks a group of students to give as many answers to a question as possible.

Thus, the methods considered are aimed at increasing the efficiency of mastering the material studied by students and stimulating them to study and master new knowledge. These methods can be used not only with students of non-linguistic universities in foreign language (English) classes, but also for studying other subjects in any educational institution with different levels of education.

When encountering new information, students should be able to think about it from all sides, from different points of view, and critically examine it. Another important fact is that critical thinking requires convincing evidence. A critical thinker finds a solution to a problem on his own and substantiates his decision with convincing and well-founded evidence. He understands that the problem can be solved differently, tries to prove that his chosen solution is stronger and more productive than others. Reasoned critical thinking should be one of the main components of a competitive bachelor's and master's training system. Understanding the role of a foreign language in the development of academic mobility of teachers and students has necessitated a study of the correspondence between the requirements of the educational program in foreign languages and the needs of the labor market and professions. It turned out that the educational programs in effect today not only for technical but also for other non-linguistic universities require updating and taking into account the key provisions of the Council of Europe documents concerning the requirements for the levels of foreign language proficiency of students participating in active international activities, including student exchanges. Consequently, interactive methods of teaching foreign language professional communication based on texts in the students' specialty can be used in non-linguistic universities of various profiles, as well as in advanced training courses for foreign language teachers.

Conclusion: Analyzing our activities in using interactive methods and pedagogical technologies, we came to the following conclusions:

- the introduction of interactive forms of pedagogical technology gives a more tangible and sustainable learning result than traditional methods;
- a situation of success is necessary for the formation of speech competence (inhibitions, self-doubt disappear, the student's self-esteem increases);
- interactive interaction involves effective factors of assistance and mutual assistance; students' learning motivation increases;
- communication skills are formed (the student expresses his thoughts, argues, i.e., reaches the level of speaking);

The main difficulties in implementing pedagogical experience are:

- the need for a lot of preliminary work by the teacher to prepare all participants in the interaction, selection and adaptation of material for work in the lesson;
 - the likelihood of both interpersonal conflicts between the participants and conflicts of interest in discussing the problem;
 - the difficulty of some topics for discussion in a foreign language due to the insufficiency of the acquired vocabulary;
 - possible passivity of some participants.
- The most important aspect of organizing interactive forms of teaching a foreign language for a teacher is the need to take into account the above-mentioned barriers when planning their lesson and timely readiness to make certain efforts to overcome them.

Thus, the fundamental aspects of the interactive approach are that individual, paired and group work can be organized in foreign language classes, research projects, role-playing games can be used, in addition, work with documents and various sources of information is carried out, creative works are used. The use of an interactive approach in teaching a foreign language undoubtedly increases the effectiveness of the pedagogical process, and also ensures the effectiveness of training, but requires the teacher to carefully prepare for the lesson and increase control over the students' activities when completing assignments.

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